

ANSAR-UD-DEEN SOCIETY OF NIGERIA

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Ansar-ud-Deen Society of Nigeria is an organization of the Muslim Intellectuals organized to advance religious education and sensitize Muslim communities on the significance of Western education, which the earliest Muslim populous rejected on condition of its intimate contact with Christian evangelism. This set Christian people to have the upper hand in educational excellence ahead of the Muslim citizens. The organization started with a sensitization campaign but metamorphosed into the reformist movement of the Islamic religion, which established branches in most of Nigeria's Muslim communities. The movement established educational institutions, published books, established healthcare centers, and constructed mosques for religious awareness and worship, which consequently advanced educational awareness among the Muslim citizens of Nigeria.

Date Range: 1923 CE - 2000 CE

Region: Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa. Most Nigerian Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Sulaiman O. Tootola, A Short Biography of Ansar-Ud-Deen Society of Nigeria, Ibadan Brach in the AR-RISALLAH COMMUNICATIONS pp.30-31
- Source 2: Islamic is our pride, Numaray International Nig. Ltd. Rashed Adesokan, Ibadan.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://litcaf.com/ansar-ud-deen/#0>
- Source 1 Description: Tope Apoola, Ansar-Ud-Deen, Litcaf.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://dbpedia.org/page/Ansar_Ud_Deen
- Source 1 Description: DBPedia.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 40

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

- ↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
 - Number of levels [numeric value]: 5
- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
 - No
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - No
 - ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
 - No
 - ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection

process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The group applied the Holy Qur'an as the divine religious guide of Islam.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Power of creating other beings.

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Yes [specify]: Nothing escapes the knowledge of the High God.
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

↳ In dreams:
– No

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

Notes: The communication comes through the Messengers and Prophets.

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– Yes [specify]: Inspiration.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– No

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - No
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They know other non-human creatures.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

- ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: Animals and Plants.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Divine prohibition is set on adultery.
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: Same-sex practices are prohibited.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: Supernatural beings care about Animals and other beings.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done on the directives of the High God.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Severe burning in the Hellfire.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: General failure in life.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - No
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: Eternal happiness in life.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
– Yes

↳ Other purpose:
– Yes [specify]: Messiah will fight the devil.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:
– No

- ↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - Yes [specify]: Only the High God knows the actual time of the eschaton.
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Peace.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 5

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 3

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized

way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group utilizes English language in addition to Arabic and Yoruba languages.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The group utilizes Islamic lunar and Gregorian calendars.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: ANSAR-UD-DEEN SOCIETY OF NIGERIA, Gbadamosi, T. G. O.. The Establishment of Western Education Among Muslims in Nigeria, 1896-1926. Nigeria: Historical Society of Nigeria and Ibadan University Press, 1967.

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